

THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF DEVELOPING STUDENTS' COLLABORATIVE SKILLS THROUGH EDUCATIONAL LESSONS.

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Abstract. *The article gives examples of methods of organizing the teaching process of educational science. The need to take into account the psychological, age characteristics of students in the use of didactic tools has been proven on the basis of examples. Effective methods and tools for organizing the teaching process are given.*

Keywords: *Renaissance, scientist, position, technology, painting, spirit, technological map, infographics, competence, media production, rubric, qualification.*

ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ РАЗВИТИЯ НАВЫКОВ СОТРУДНИЧЕСТВА УЧАЩИХСЯ ПОСРЕДСТВОМ УЧЕБНЫХ ЗАНЯТИЙ.

Аннотация. *В статье приведены примеры методов организации учебного процесса педагогической науки. На примерах доказана необходимость учета психологических, возрастных особенностей учащихся при использовании дидактических средств. Приведены эффективные методы и инструменты организации учебного процесса.*

Ключевые слова: *Возрождение, учёный, позиция, технология, живопись, позиция, дух, технологическая карта, инфографика, компетентность, медиапродукция, рубрика, квалификация.*

In the essence of the main content of many reforms implemented in our country, the measures taken, large-scale works. At the heart of it, of course, is the "Human factor". Our President Sh. Mirziyoyev making radical changes in the life of our country with his initiatives, The work of our great scholars and scholars who lived in our country in order to continue the foundation stones of the III Renaissance together with the youth the representative of every field, the soul of his country, [1] The issue of implementation together with dedicated people has its relevance and shows its importance more deeply. The essence of the educational process is a person, his harmonious perfection in all aspects in come and well-being, conditions for the realization of personal interests and creation of effective mechanisms, outdated thinking and social behavior to change the patterns of the reforms implemented in our country is considered as the main goal and driving force.

The content of education and its effectiveness are of great importance in our country given, the views of the state education standard curricula in the new version is being put into practice as an experiment. In the design of "Education" lessons introduced in schools, its main the students of the lessons in order to fully absorb the ideas and goals into the minds of the students to each student, based on age, physiological condition it is important to organize classes based on an individual approach. He learns by looking at the "Education" books that are used in practice primary grade (A2), ninth grade (A2+), eleventh grade (V1) minimum qualification requirements, competencies, assessment for a graduate compliance with the procedure and educational programs, and each stage is spiritual and moral, thinking, legal, civil, economic, physical, ecological, aesthetic types of education let's see what it contains.[2] At each stage, students are taught national

and universal values to educate in the spirit of respect; Family and school in the education of students to strengthen mutually effective cooperation, to parents, other nationalities and based on the universal principle of respect for representatives of culture support for formation; protection of children's rights and their ensuring legal interests, "From national recovery to national rise" a number of ideas such as inculcating national values based on the principle we can see.

These are the tasks that are required of us pedagogues are the following:

- students in all aspects, physically, mentally, spiritually and morally adaptation to social life through development and in various complex situations teach to make the right decision; active civic positions in the child forming;

- world religions have been passed down from generation to generation for many centuries along with explaining that it is a spiritual value, in no other world religion explaining that the ideas of violence, terrorism and extremism are not propagated;

- cooperation with social and educational institutions in personal activities strengthening; he has moral and moral problems or in his upbringing

Children with gaps or troubled families are prone to crime individual work with young people who are or are on the prevention list. It is gratifying that it is a worthy assistant manual in our tasks. Formation of an active citizenship position in

education students, support for their comprehensive socialization, effective cooperation to do, meaningful organization of time, national, spiritual and universal respect values, realize their intellectual and creative potential serves to issue. In addition, providing students with quality education, guide them to the right path of education, have the necessary knowledge and life skills helping them to become independent, to adapt to independent life, various making decisions based on legal and moral criteria in situations aesthetically and modernly decorated, aimed at the formation of skills, rich in interesting and psychological-pedagogical materials.

The educational-methodological complex is the main part of the state policy in the field of education created on the basis of principles; mental and physical capabilities of students, taking into account age, psychophysiological characteristics, level of education, interests, abilities received; the feeling of patriotism and national pride in students aimed at formation; that the required volume of general secondary education is provided, students' independent creative thinking, organizational skills and practical experience orientation to the development of skills; content of topics efficient of consistency, advanced pedagogical technologies, media products it is acknowledged that it has been used.

Illustrations in the form of pictures: maps, drawings, schemes, media products consisting of tables, diagrams, photos, infographics it is decorated with new, suitable for the level of psychophysiological development of students in the form of a glossary of concepts, terms, rules, definitions and the like expression further expands the sphere of influence of science. The fact that it reflects the latest achievements of science and technology, educational science that the content integrity of the subjects is ensured, the subjects of the academic subject are literary in a simple, simple, understandable and fluent language, strictly following the rules of the language being stated, following a logical sequence and consistency the fact that it is covered by the content will strengthen the mastery of the science.

With appropriate illustrations that do not contradict the mentality of the Uzbek people enrichment, clear presentation of questions and tasks, students thinking, writing, describing, drawing, calculating, practical work from pedagogical technologies in teaching to perform and conduct experiments. It is intended to be used to educate students in the spirit of patriotism will help more. To express the same concept with two different terms, that inaccuracy in quoting dates is not allowed, students text and pictures, explanatory dictionary, aimed at developing technical creativity, logical and innovative thinking covering design and modeling tasks of the child helps to adapt to social life and expand the worldview. Interactive methods, innovative pedagogical technologies in the educational process and attention to the use of information technologies in the educational process is increasing day by day.

One of the reasons for this is traditional if students are taught to acquire only ready-made knowledge in education, deep knowledge of modern technologies mastering, independent study and analysis, great creative conclusions also teaches them to release. In this process, the teacher develops the personality, creates conditions for formation, education and upbringing, as well as performs the function of controllability and orientation. Educational lessons are creative, non-traditional conversation, game, in the family, in nature, debate, it is desirable that it should be in the form of a discussion, a meeting. Why use pedagogical technologies in education classes attention is paid to:

1. Clarity of the educational goal in the lesson;
2. Compliance of the content of pedagogical technology with the requirements of the current period;
3. Didactic rules in the process of pedagogical technology;

When using pedagogical technology, the teacher follows the following rules should do:

1. Modernity is an experience based on the practice of education and training introduction of innovations in the field of past didactics;
2. Continuous updating of educational content. To educational programs study carefully without being indifferent;
3. To study new creations in the field of general and national values;
4. Optimizing the activity of the student and the teacher during the educational process, activation. Expanding their internal mentality and level of education;
5. Scientism – a new method using motor problem cases, teaching students independent thinking and self-awareness;
6. To do this, involve children in practical activities based on the topics of the program it is important to achieve;
7. Clarity of the purpose of the lesson, modernity of the content, national enrichment with spiritual values, independent creative activity of students, in the lesson in the rubric "Folk oral creativity": the appropriate use of proverbs, fairy tales, use of games, test questions, visual aids, questions and tasks;
8. Every teacher to implement new pedagogical technology it is necessary to have deep theoretical knowledge in teaching education. So education classes can be organized in different ways.

Education classes for primary school students in different forms can be organized:

1. Game, conversation, meeting, debate, in the family, in public places, in neighborhoods organizing events. Clarity, historicity and focusing on educating the concepts of manners with modernity.

2. Educational sessions in the form of audio, video, live chat and exhibition organization.

3. The teacher should have new technological skills and creativity. How to achieve the goal of the teacher and the student. It is up to them to choose the technology, because it is the main of both parties. The goal is to achieve a specific result, in which the students. The technology used is selected depending on the level, character of the team, conditions. For example, to achieve the result, maybe work with a computer, maybe a movie (handout, drawing, various literature) will be needed. That's all depends on the teacher and the student. At the same time, the study subject is unique aspect, place and conditions, the ability and needs of the main student and should take into account the ability to organize cooperative activities. Only then, the desired guaranteed result can be achieved. Primary education lesson type, purpose, for using pedagogical technologies in their classes, it is natural to dwell on the topic.

First of all, this lesson is technological we need to make a map. Because the technological memory of the lesson is each the topic, the subject taught for each lesson, the nature of the subject, It is made based on the students' ability and needs. It is up to the teacher how to make the technological map of the lesson depends on experience, goal, creativity and discretion. Technological map no matter how it is structured, it should reflect the lesson process as a whole and there must be a clearly defined goal, task and guaranteed result.

The technology of organizing the lesson should be fully expressed. The structure of the technological map allows the teacher to develop the extended lesson frees from drawing and writing, because such a map shows the lesson process and all aspects of student and teacher activities are reflected.

REFERENCES

1. Speech of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev at the ceremony dedicated to the Day of Teachers and Coaches. September 30, 2020. <http://marifat.uz/marifat/ruknlar/rasmiy/4939.htm>
2. UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (UNCPRD) December 13, 2006.
3. 3. Concept of development of inclusive education in the public education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2020-2025. (<https://lex.uz/docs/-5044711>)
4. Azizxo'jayeva N.N. Pedagogik texnologiyalar va pedagogik mahorat. T. 2006 y. 5. Ro'ziyeva D va b. 3-sinf tarbiya fani darsligi. T. «SANO-STANDART». 2020 y
5. Abdullaeva B. S. et al. The specifics of modern legal education and upbringing of schoolchildren in the countries of the post-soviet world // Journal of Advanced Research in Dynamical and Control Systems. – 2020. – T. 12. – №. 2. – C.2706-2714.